

Full title: Creating museums without the museum: use of common communication devices for democratization of heritage

Short title (for running page headers): Creating museums without the museum

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Abstract:

The aim of our research project is to develop a platform based on open source software to accede to online information on a subject or object with a general communication device for consumer use, such as PDAs, mobile telephones or others that provide a GPS function. Our goal is to aid the opening of micro museums for promotor with little budgets, by doing the publication of information for the promotor easier and for the visitor more accessible. This platform may allow visitors to automatically locate and accede to information published as public domain contain (in different formats: image, text, audio...). This is an advance for institutions, for communities and young initiatives with small or poor budgets which could offer information as exhibition support or to create a guide tour with maps, text, audio, images and video support based on free information and open source software.

Introduction

The aim of our research project, which its first results we could like to present here, is to develop a platform based on open source software to accede to online information on a topic or object with a general communication device for consumer use, such PDAs, mobile telephones and others provided with GPS function. The idea is to take advance of the actual disposal of resources (communication gadgets, software facilities and online information) focused to ensure a wider knowledge of heritage even in this cases where the creation of a museum is not possible due to limited access to economic resources; in other words, the use of common communication devices for democratization of heritage.

Information is given in museums under three principles: first, information is provided by one institution which represents a community (one voice with one discourse, which offers competent but mostly univocal information on a subject), second, museums are institutions which demand wide resources, and third, museums are nowadays conceived as closed boxes with flexible shows and installations with complementary activities but restricted to a fixed location. In other worlds, a given community projects itself as an identity, providing the ground elements to be categorized as (material or immaterial) heritage by a museum. This elaborate the discourse on the community's identity, selects the adequate items, explain them (information), and put them to exhibition on a space by using physical and organizational facilities (infrastructure).

Fig. 1 Conventional museum

We would like to define democratization of heritage as process which may allow any community to show its own heritage, to create its own discourse (as a unique voice or as multiple voices) and without the need of expensive infrastructure. The communication technology is getting more and more present in our lives, it is a fact that not all the world population has access to such devices, but it is also true that they are getting more and more popular and it seems to be a growing phenomenon. And on the other hand, we may consider that leisure traveling and tourism is more frequent in population with higher economic levels.

Our goal is to create a platform in open source software for general communication device for consumer use (such PDAs, mobile telephones and others) provided with GPS function which may allow visitors to automatically locate and accede to information published as public domain contain in different formats, f.e. as exhibition support or to create a guide tour with maps, text, audio, images and video support. This would promote the opening of micro museums with poor economical resources by facilitating to the museum the publication of information and to the visitors the access to information. Institutions, communities and young initiatives with small or poor budgets could take advance of this platform. The principle of this project is to bring information to the visitor visiting a given place (temple, local market, natural space...), thus to show heritage in every-day-life environments or there where conventional musealization isn't possible: to create a museum without a museum.

Fig. 2 Museum without museum

In this case, the community self directly elaborates its own discourse on identity, providing the items for exhibition or to visit, possibly on their usual environment, and with a minimum of infrastructure (physical: device with digital camera and voice recorder or video recorder features, computer facilities and internet connection, and organizational: team responsible for information). By using these facilities the community may create the online information which support the discourse on a given environment. The visitor, on the other hand, brings with the device to accede to the information: the general communication device for consumer use provided with GPS function (hardware) and the platform in open source software. In other words, the project leads with the creation of public domain museums.

Popularization of general communication device with GPS function

Since 1997 the use of portable communication devices have been continuously increasing(1). Not only the expansion and popularization of PDAs, mobile telephones and other devices provided with GPS function has been constant, also the inclusion of new standards and features is a growing market. New devices operate more as multimedia devices with internet access than conventional portable telephones. The upcoming generation of cellular phones and PDAs include mostly features that overtake the common phone function, like GPS and access to mobile internet. All that supposes possibilities to the general user, and in our case not only for the visitor, but also for the people creating contains on material or immaterial heritage thanks to features like image or video capturing, audio recording, mapping... in the same way as nowadays citizen journalism has bloomed, anybody with a middle standard mobile communication device can report about a new event or new and share the information online for the general public.

Fig. 3 Based on a middle standard model of a mobile telephone leader company

Nowadays the frequent use of such devices with GPS and multimedia functions added to the access to public online information via internet open a wide range of educational possibilities. Instead of looking for new technologies for us searching for new uses of pre-existing common technologies supposes a very interesting field of development, trying to maximize the present hardware and software. Thus general communication devices for consumer use with GPS function join the advances of portability, acquaintance of use and access to de-located information (even with some geographical restrictions).

Existing experiences

In the last years the introduction of audio-guides have changed(2), in some way, the way museums are visited(3), specially by the fact of giving the information in different languages and allowing visitors to personalize the guided visit (at least in tempo and selection, or skipping of information). However audio-guides are a step forward on accessibly but in a limited form: on one hand, information is only disposed as audio file (no other type of contents could be shown and it may be also a handicap for hearing impaired who cannot mostly accede to alternative information formats)(4) and on the other hand, they demand a large investment on devices, this is not affordable for many museums with poor economic resources. In many cases audio-guides acquisitions are a mere complement to conventional text panels, thus a way of offering the same information, or kind of information, on a more advanced support. There where space to visit is larger some museums, but also touristic points of interest like cities or natural parks, it is possible to find some experiences on audio-guides as downloadable audio files for general communication devices for consumer use. Sometimes the audio-files are accessible only at the place of exhibition and for standard audio-guides (restricted access)(5), but other times they are accessible via internet from the sites of the promoters, totally or partially for free(6). This last option should be seriously taken in consideration as a promotional

strategy, targeted not to actual visitors but to the achievement of potential visitors who previously get in contact with the institution or place of interest via internet.

Other kinds of services of very different nature of audio-guides, but leading in the same direction, are the coming services related to the GPS function in general communication devices. Basically a GPS works as a locator in different ways, in its original and basic level the user is located on the terrain; in the second level, the user is located in reference to, at least, to points, locating the user between A and B, this is the use for trip planning; in the third level, the device locates also points of interest (services like banks, drugstores...) close to the user, and in the last level, the GPS locate preselected information around the user (services, see-sightings, tracks, pictures of the landscape and monuments, complementary maps...). In other words, in the communication device the GPS function locates the points and the multimedia features displays the information in different image formats.

A step forward in this direction, ahead of usual audio-guides in specific devices, is the use of conventional mobile telephones and PDAs with video function as support for digital guides. In addition, GPS, bluetooth and Wi-Fi make it possible to link information to pre-given locations. This supposed that promoters and institutions do not need to provide the devices to visitors, saving funds and enabling the visitor to manage gadgets they are familiar to. Already some of the commercial devices are paying a main attention to the use of GPS functions, and especially for pedestrians, which is the regular way of mobility on visiting museums. This requires some technical improvements and complications compared to GPS devices for vehicle, thus pedestrians are more difficult to locate by satellites due technical and environmental reasons(7). It may be of interest just to see two examples of this GPS uses in devices being now introduced into the consumer market, and already in improvement.

Nokia Maps™. Nokia Maps (and Ovi Maps™) a map and route planning application restricted to Nokia devices. With this application the user can download maps of countries in the five continents with detailed road and city maps, the user can also store and manage favorite locations, calculate routes between two points. It also offers other added services under fees like: traffic information in real time, as well as, optional city guides, which can also show other kind of information like photos, video clips and audio files. The next generation of mobile phones with GPS function points to a satellite navigation gadget with complex features, as f. e. service location, with other user, information shared between users and so on. This application was conceived also for pedestrian use(8).

iPhone™. The iPhone 3G is also a device that offers similar services by running specific applications. The iPhone locates the users via GPS or via triangulation by using Wi-Fi nets and boosters for mobile devices, it was developed paying great attention to the information shared between users. Users can mark a location, save and share it with other people. An advanced research function allows users to locate points of interest close to them by keyword(9).

Albentdecker™. The Alb Natural Park (Germany) has introduced a GPS device with multimedia features running under the software Albentdecker(10). Based on the GPS function the Albentdecker

locates the user on the Alb Natural Park and shows him/her full functional hiking tracks on virtual maps, natural guide and learning resources in different multimedia formats in the multimedia display. This platform was designed mainly for educational purposes and targeted to the younger population(11).

Google Android™ and Mobilyzy™. Mobilizy(12) has developed an application for the operative system Android(13) calls Wikitude AR Travel Guide(14). It works like as mobile guide in an augmented virtuality based on Wikipedia(15), Qype(16) and Panoramio(17), basically the application allows the user to find tags close to the user's location and to show the contents linked to them in augmented virtuality at the device. The tags include annotations, descriptions and complementary information.

Openmoko™. Openmoko Freerunner (GTA2)(18) is a prototype of a mobile telephone with GPS function programmable in open software. A project in development(19) may create a program which may make it possible for the user to automatically accede to information published in Wikipedia or in other sites with public domain information. The device would locate the position of the visitor and the points of interest close to him/her and it would be able to show information according to tags pre-defined by the user/visitor. An alert service would notify the user the disposal of information by clicking on a link or as text or audio file to download.

Limitations

Like explained at the beginning of the paper we could like to make it clear that our analysis and platform proposal may be taken in consideration as a help to open museums there where basically the access to economical resources are limited, and it is not conceived as an alternative to conventional museums, but support to these communities or initiatives that cannot afford a conventional museum. Essentially, our guideline in this project is to lead with a deficit in infrastructure, thus to facilitate the access to information on material and immaterial heritage. Obviously a main aspect to be taken in consideration is the question on the quality of exhibited items and of information and there the museums could grant a significant assistance for raising museums without museums by providing the appropriate scientific knowledge. The central point we could like to present here is the way of acceding to information and none of the above shoved applications, devices or platforms seem to achieve a real solution to the basic problem: the democratization of museums.

All the applications, platforms and devices above have some limitation that restricts their use for the most of the consumers. Commercial solutions where the visitor could provide the device only works on the devices of the same company and advances features, needed for our purposes are not inexpensive for promoters and users. Even platforms are not flexible enough designed to be universally implemented for virtual exhibition aims. Specific platforms like Albentdecker is also commercial solution, that demand information adapted to the device, and this has to be provided by the promoters. An open source solution, like Mobilizy, works only in gadgets running Android. Furthermore, the other alternative for Openmoko is a project for a device full programmed in open source but Openmoko Freerunner (GTA2) itself is still a prototype.

Looking for alternatives

The above related experiences may show that there is a theoretical way to create an alternative to conventional museums based on (public) information accessible online and to relate this information to user's location. As concept such virtual museum it may be real in the next times. For us the main point is not how to digitize and to de-locate museums but how to guarantee sharing cultural heritage in contexts where promoters have little economical resources by using the possibilities provided by the communications technologies. This leads us not to develop specific devices or applications (restricted to some companies or to programming software) but to achieve the most universal solution based on common communication devices, open source software and access to public domain information.

Our aim is to develop a platform agent that could able the user to information on points of interest close in a given location. This platform is needed to allow the most of the users (if not any) to accede to information, this means that is has to be a cross platform, it may work in any device independently of the operating software. Due to a dual system the user could locate the museum previous to the visit on the internet in its own site or in an open location service (like wikiloc)(20) or being located by the GPS function *in situ* and get the information via a mobile internet connection. The visitor could pre-defined tags on points of interest, one time the location is found on the internet or arrived by the visitor the information items could be listed at the display and finally the visitor could select the items to be showed or played. The kind of information showed could be of a wide spectrum from text to maps, video, photo or audio files and integrated in different formats (.html, .gxm, .kml, .jpeg, .flv...).

The promotor, promoting community or group, would elaborate the information according to the formats supported by the chosen public domain service, f.e. photos (in .tiff, .jpeg formats) and tracks (in .gpx or .kml formats) on an internet site. Sites like wikipedia, wikicommons(21), or wikiloc make possible the publication of information in different formats, especially of interest under the point of view of a museum: texts, maps and tracks, photos, audio or even video files. Such type of files can be mostly displayed or played by the upcoming mobile devices for communication general use, now the forthcoming uses of these features have to be researched and established.

Fig. 4 Two ways of acceding to the information

Let us suppose that an open source museum promotor (a community or a group) have already creating a museum without a museum. All the information on heritage: presentation texts, explanation video, photos of objects, tracks through a landscape, songs and any item of information the promotor considers relevant can be uploaded or presented in an internet site (even touristic information on arriving or transport connection could be included). All this information is given tags (public domain museum -is our first recommendation-, heritage, vernacular architecture, folk music, medicinal plants...) that categorize the information by contains, thus anybody can 'call' the information given around a geographical area without having a clear idea of the detailed contain.

When acceding to the information prior to the visit, the visitor would download the information on the open source museum (partial or totally) to the device. Ones at the location the user would be able to accede to the information manually or by using the GPS function, in this case, the agent would locate the visitor and according to the pre-selected tags would shown the information items that the visitor may read or play by selecting the appropriate file. This means that the internet connection is not done by the device which represents a major advantage in environments where access to mobile internet is not available or in situations where mobile internet cannot be afforded by the user.

When acceding *in situ* the visitor is firstly located by the GPS function. By filtering the information by the preselected tags according to the preferences of the visitor, the agent would identify from the public domain site what kind of information were at disposal and select it to be showed at the device's display. In this case not all the files are downloaded, the platform displays the links to the related files, so that the visitor could select the desired items to accede to. For this way of acceding to information an internet connection is needed, not previously, to the visit but during the visit. This supposes an advance for the user in the sense of providing the most actual information and saving the previous selection and downloading of information. On the other hand, it subordinates the visit to the possibility

and quality of mobile internet access what may be only fulfilled in restricted locations, range bounded by the quality of connection, even limited by simple geographical variables.

The present technical development is being done in order to know what possibilities there are for an universal platform, thus a cross platform that could work in any kind of device independently of operating software and hardware, to avoid developing a platform only operative in limited devices of one company. In fact the challenge is not to accede and to share information via mobile device on the internet, but to do it in an universal and open way. The alternatives being analyzed in the present are:

(i) A platform located in the device, an extra installed program in the device programmed in open software this software package included a central running agent, that leads with the tasks of acceding to the information and secondary programs that works as code translator, to make possible that any device could be able to run the agent without any restriction due running system or company. All the process would be hold at the device.

(ii) A platform located at a internet site where the public domain information is published. The agent would 'wake up' when some device is located via GPS and allows the connection. Connected to the provider of the service pop-up windows will open in the internet browser of the device. The information to be linked will be showed on the display. This would work as some kind of assisted internet site to be browsed by the visitor.

Conclusions

Still being in the first stage of development the proposed platform would transform general communication device for consumer use, such PDAs, mobile telephones or others provided with GPS function in portable museums. There are some initiatives (commercial and non commercial) that target to services that are in the ground of the present project. GPS function and mobiles internet access open a window to the use of such devices as travel guides and complex satellite navigation gadgets. The main problem most of this developments is the restricted possibility of further development, thus such guides are restricted to some kind of devices or the guide programs are very limited, not in features but in accessibility to public domain information on line or to not by the companies predetermine information or services.

A platform, like the proposed, may be possible to create museums without museums or public domain museums. The access through general communication device for consumer use with GPS function to information on heritage in a given location give not only to the visitor the possibility to achieve new knowledge on a community or group, but also, and fundamentally, to allow communities and groups with poor budgets the opening of museums in every-day-life environments. Therefore, many communities could create their own virtual museums with information on the web; information that could previously downloaded or automatically located and acceded via internet *in situ*. With this platform micro museums ad hoc, natural spaces, open air museums or points of interest or a guided tour outdoors could be created anywhere without infrastructure at the place. This points to the democratization and universalization of heritage and museums, thus a museum could be opened or

found anywhere, and given information could come from different points of view. This could be especially interesting to areas and communities with no facilities and economic support to open a conventional museum.

Notes

(1) In developed countries the mobile telephone subscribers per inhabitant in 1977 was 18%, in 2007 97%, in developing countries in 1997 1%, in 2007 45%, and in general term in the whole world was in 1997 4%, in 2007 49%. International Telecommunication Union, <http://itu.int/ITU-D/ict/statistics/ict/graphs/mobile/jpg> (consulted 23rd April 2009).

(2) Nadeau (1989)

(3) Puig, et al. (2009)

(4) Massaro (1998) found that the use of an animated face in an application for the hearing impaired may improved the efficiency of communication.

(5) Like the Metropolitan Museum of Art: <http://www.metmuseum.org/visit/audioguide> (consulted 5th Mai 2009).

(6) Like the Guggenheim Museum in Bilbao:

<http://www.guggenheim-bilbao.es/secciones/multimedia/moviles.php?idioma=es> (consulted 5th Mai 2009), or or Madrid City: <http://www.esmadrid.com/es/portal.do?TR=C&IDR=992&IDM=971&NM=2> (consulted 5th Mai 2009).

(7) Teasley (2009).

(8) <http://spain.nokia.es/sites/micrositeNokiaMaps/> (consulted 17th June 2009), <http://maps.ovi.com/services> (consulted 2nd August 2009).

(9) <http://www.apple.com/es/iphone/features/maps.html> (consulted 17th June 2009).

(10) 'Albentdecker' literally Albfinder (like pathfinder), the Alb ist a mountain area and natural park in south Germany.

(11) <http://www.nabu-albentdecker.de> (consulted 9th March 2009).

(12) <http://www.mobilizy.com/> (consulted 17th June 2009).

(13) <http://www.google.com/mobile/android/> (consulted 17th June 2009).

(14) <http://www.mobilizy.com/wikitude.php> (consulted 17th June 2009).

(15) <http://www.wikipedia.org> (consulted 23rd June 2009).

(16) <http://www.qype.com> (consulted 23rd June 2009).

(17) <http://www.panoramio.com> (consulted 23rd June 2009).

(18) <http://www.openmoko.com/product.html> (consulted 17th June 2009).

(19) <http://cofundos.org/project.php?id=166> (consulted 17th June 2009).

(20) <http://www.wikiloc.com> (consulted 23rd June 2009).

(21) <http://commons.wikimedia.org> (consulted 23rd June 2009).

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This paper was partially supported by the Galician Government under the grant 08SIN009305PR